

Appendix A: LDA results studied and validated by the case-company stakeholders

Figure 1 Top 10 keywords in “Issue Description” field for Mantis 2016

Figure 2 Relations between “Issue Description” topics and “Test Feedback” tokens for Mantis 2016

Figure 3 Top 10 keywords in “Issue Description” field for Mantis 2017

Figure 4 Relations between “Issue Description” topics and “Test Feedback” tokens for Mantis 2017

Figure 5 Top 10 keywords in “Issue Description” field for Mantis 2018

Figure 6 Relations between “Issue Description” topics and “Test Feedback” tokens for Mantis 2018

Appendix B: Mantis topics, the representative tokens, and their interpretation

No.	Labels	<i>issueDescription</i> tokens	<i>testFeedback</i> tokens	Practitioners' Interpretation
Mantis 2016 subset				
1	Diagram	<i>impossible, diagram, unmask, association, menu</i>	<i>org.eclipse.e4, xnldiagramreader.java, gmcompositenode.java</i>	Implementation of the tool's <i>diagram</i> component
2	<i>Modelio</i> extensions	<i>module, project, stereotype, api, macos</i>	<i>api</i>	<i>Modelio</i> API to integrate new functionality
3	Core feature / Integration	<i>request, feature, links, namespacing, project</i>	<i>modelio.app, module, metamodel, index</i>	Integration aspects of the tool and model storage layers
4	Project configuration	<i>sequence, error, test, messages, keys, fragment</i>	<i>resources</i>	Project configuration and its external elements
5	Interoperability, Import/export	<i>mode, export, displayed, simple, audit</i>	<i>Windows 7/10, reproducible,</i>	OS incompatibilities and issue reproducibility in different environment / version of <i>Modelio</i>
6	Model creation	<i>command, element, user, missing, content, empty</i>	<i>* tokens are too generic to identify any relation</i>	NA
Mantis 2017 subset				
1	Project lifecycle	<i>project, view, window, import, symbol</i>	<i>*tokens are too generic to identify any relation</i>	NA
2	Diagram	<i>diagram, link, note, creation, editor</i>	<i>architecture, cursor, creation, link</i>	<i>Diagrams</i> worked on during the development in 2017
3	Workbench support	<i>create, wrong, impossible, mode, workbench</i>	<i>modelio.app</i>	Feature containing <i>workbench</i> implementation
4	BPMN metamodel evolution	<i>bpmn, flow, message, sequence, task</i>	<i>*tokens are too generic to identify any relation</i>	NA
5	BPMN metamodel evolution	<i>bpmn, process, diagram, model, collaboration</i>	<i>link, diagrams, direction, imported</i>	BPMN diagram implementation and import/export feature
6	ArchiMate metamodel support	<i>box, creating, error, archimate, edition</i>	<i>* tokens are too generic to identify any relation</i>	NA
7	BPMN diagrams	<i>element, links, bpmn, npe, lane</i>		
Mantis 2018 subset				
1	General customer support	<i>sequence, select, fragment, svn, combined</i>	<i>mail, insist, customer-name</i>	Customer relations
2	BPMN metamodel	<i>bpmn, diagram, phd, diagrams, collaboration</i>	<i>*tokens are too generic to identify any relation</i>	NA
3	Methodological links	<i>methodology, link, icon, field, methodological</i>		
4	<i>Modelio</i> module (extensions for <i>Modelio</i>)	<i>element, multiple, box, metaclass, edition</i>	<i>studio, module, test, expertise</i>	Solution dedicated for the tool's module development
5	Document view	<i>archimate, npe, click, view, user</i>	<i>* tokens are too generic to identify any relation</i>	NA
6	Collaborative work / constellation	<i>project, constellation, feature, button, impossible</i>	<i>test, constellation, clients, api</i>	Collaborative work with Constellation
7	Diagrams	<i>creation, diagram, description, links, unmasked</i>	<i>org.eclipse.e4, abstractlayertransform, abstractindexlayertransform</i>	<i>Diagrams</i> definition, implementation, commands and controllers in Eclipse RCP